

QUALITY EDUCATION THROUGHOUT LIFE

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Abstract. *In order to save children from negative vices and motivate them to positive ones, the teacher should use the method of providing them with material encouraging creativity and stimulating the future. Giving children freedom is an effective tool in the formation of personality. The main task of the school teacher is to teach and direct the student to perform the task while providing the necessary material. The use of such methods in literature classes greatly helps the student in mastering the texts in the textbooks through creativity*

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In the 21st century, education on a global scale is recognized as the main and relevant factor that ensures sustainable systematic development, and in the new education concept set by most countries until 2030, "Creating the opportunity to receive quality education throughout life" process is defined as a task that cannot be delayed. For this purpose, in our republic, special attention is being paid to further improvement of the teaching methodology, gradual application of the principles of individualization to educational processes, introduction of the latest modern information, communication and innovative technologies into the educational system. As everyone knows due to objective and subjective reasons, such as difficulties associated with the transition from one management system to another, temporary economic stress, kindness, humanity, compassion, mutual assistance, eventually weaken somewhat. On the contrary, it is necessary to educate young people in the spirit of life-giving ideas in the works of great thinkers, to inculcate the spirit of humanity and patriotism in their hearts, in order to eliminate the growing individualism, thinking only about one's own interests, and prioritizing material well-being.

In fact, such problems have always existed, only the ways of solving them have changed. "A set of measures used to overcome a certain obstacle in achieving a goal is called a method." sometimes we call this situation "system of methods, i.e. methodology".

In order to save children from negative vices and motivate them to positive ones, the teacher should use the method of providing them with material encouraging creativity and stimulating the future. Giving children freedom is an effective tool in the formation of personality. The main task of the school teacher is to teach and direct the student to perform the task while providing the necessary material. The use of such methods in literature classes greatly helps the student in mastering the texts in the textbooks through creativity.

As school and life ensure mutual connection of education, there are social-pedagogical, psychological-didactic conditions for organizing literature classes based on today's requirements. According to socio-pedagogical conditions, the teacher should be creative, have professional skills, have sufficient methodical knowledge, should be able to establish a friendly relationship with the student, and the institution should have new generation textbooks, visual aids, technical tools, meeting the normative (normative) requirements in accordance with modern requirements. a classroom, a healthy psychological environment, comfortable conditions, the existence of a

sincere relationship between a teacher and a student, and behavior directed at mutual respect and cooperation should exist. All of the above requirements combine to create a beautiful educational effect.

It is appropriate for the literature teacher to enter this process by developing literary and aesthetic thinking in young people. For example, a pedagogue can start the word with Ahmed Yassavi. He said that the creator's year of birth is unknown, that he died in 1167, that he is a great figure of Sufism poetry, that in his wisdom he interpreted divine enlightenment through the symbols of the four elements - earth, water, air and fire, and that for Yassavi, the earth was a symbol of the original Motherland. students will be able to:

*My head is numb, I am numb, my body is numb,
My soul is tired because I can't tell the truth!*

Here, Hazrat said, "I am made of the soil, I walk on it, I am as valuable and humble as the soil. "One day, I will return to my homeland - my land," he says. Also, we can dwell on the work and life path of Sadriddin Ainiy, a teacher of literature, a linguist, a scholar of literature, an orientalist, who expressed the ideas of patriotism, humanity, and philanthropy in his works, who believed that the main goal of education is to make a child mature by being loyal to the motherland and the people. Drawing the attention of students to Aini's opinion that patriotism means loving the motherland, protecting it from enemies, and sacrificing one's life for its development, "Be motivated to study, be a man. After that, you will serve your country until you are strong..." will be a major educational goal.

In the course of scientific research, it became clear that the way of life and work of the creators of the first 10 years of the last century in the 1990s is the most suitable and effective way to instill the love of the Motherland in the hearts of young people. Therefore, the teacher of literature should thoroughly know the history of modern literature, should achieve the mastery of works and works of writers like Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Fitrat, Cholpon, Abdulla Qadiri, Usman Nasir, Hamza.

In the course of literary education, students should be taught that the Motherland is sacred for every person, that each of us can understand the meaning of our life by living in the Motherland, feel and understand the world, and thus have a worldview, introduce the conditions of the development of the Motherland, and awaken in them the need to fulfill those conditions.

As a matter of fact, there is no final, strict, universal definition of homeland and patriotism in science. Everyone defines it as they understand it. This gives the literature teacher the freedom of thought, but also imposes on him the responsibility of providing a common understanding that corresponds to the worldview of the students of the entire class.

When creating a method of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism in literature classes, it can be envisaged to activate students or learners through the following effective methods:

- Determining the characteristics of patriotism: human patriotism is divided into types; in the form of attitude towards nature, the soil where he was born and raised, towards his relatives; Protecting the Motherland, maintaining the peace of the Motherland, attitude to various wrong and destructive ideas, attitude to national values and others; Such as attitude to the defense of the homeland;
- Comparison of the relationship between patriotism and the character traits of other nationalities: to study the similarities and differences of patriotism in the character of heroes of

other nations and our own character-characteristics, to consider them as an example of the interpretation of the heroes of a work of art;

- Studying the sequence system of giving patriotism in class sections: forming a sense of patriotism by getting to know the beauty of nature, taking into account the age characteristics of the 5th graders;
- In the 6th grade, to inculcate the ideas of patriotism through heroic tales and legends, in the 7th grade, to promote patriotism through loyalty to the motherland, the bravery of our national heroes;
- In the 8th-9th grades, to introduce students to the essence of the idea of patriotism through the analysis of the works in which the ideas of love for the Motherland are inculcated in the sojourn;
- In grades 10-11, focus on understanding the philosophy of patriotism through examples of fiction infused with the ideas of duty, loyalty, and spiritual maturity;
- To guide young people of academic lyceum and vocational education to experience various events, the indelible, instructive aspects of patriotism presented in artistic works, the issue of using educational exercises, comparative analysis of the fate of people who have fallen into a bad situation, are far away from their homeland, and are in difficult conditions. It is necessary to pay attention and select and teach the works of this content.

Fulfillment of these requirements is the moral duty of every patriotic citizen of Uzbekistan to be taught at every stage of literary education, and patriotism is "understanding and wanting and supporting the unity of the national state - Uzbekistan; understanding of single civil responsibility; Be able to relate to the history, present and future of Uzbekistan; conscious participation in work and events related to patriotism; Enthusiasm for Uzbekistan; possession of harmonious personal goals aimed at the benefit of the homeland; Faith in the future of Uzbekistan, its greatness; to be able to show a negative attitude towards blasphemy, Motherland, Uzbekistan, humiliation of compatriots, lack of love for the motherland" It must be understood that it consists of

In response to such spiritual needs, various works are being created in literary science, and teachers are referring to them in their activities. This ensures that the theoretical basis of the training is thorough. For example, A. Ibrohimov, H. Sultanov, N. Joraevs sense of country "if we take his work. It expresses national values, customs and traditions specific to the past, present and future of independent Uzbekistan. At the same time, the book contains rich factual materials and historical documents about the origins of the Uzbek people, the great contributions of our great ancestors to the universal development, the role of spirituality in the history of the new Uzbek state, the antiquity and continuity of our statehood, the fate of thousands of brave people who died fighting bravely for their freedom and their faith. based on live footage and original sources.

Authors M. Kuronov, A. Akmalov, A. Redjaboev «Our national qualities, how to love the Motherland?" The brochure is aimed at forming youth's devotion to their Motherland, the ideology of national independence, and the feeling of the Motherland. It can be used by the literature teacher of UOTM in the process of planning "How to love the Motherland?", "What is the Motherland?", "What is the Motherland?", patriotic ideas in the works of poets, writers, and the scientific heritage of our scientists.

According to the psychological and didactic conditions of teaching literature, the student's knowledge should be leveled, he should be able to perform educational exercises based on cooperation, he should feel the need to acquire new knowledge, the teacher should follow the

didactic principles, and he should have the qualification of purposeful use of methods and forms in the lesson.

It is also necessary to consider the use of theatrical productions. In any case, in upper grades and academic lyceum students will begin to choose certain specializations for their future. He will begin to decide what, where and how to start his future lifestyle. Moods of going to other places to study and choosing a profession appear. He feels the need to go far away from the place where he was born, his friends, his favorite school. He also thinks about his destiny related to his chosen profession, calculates his opportunities, family situation, everything. When looking at this issue from the point of view of patriotism, it is observed that the period of change occurs in the youth. Therefore, the selection of literary material suitable for their situation, their content in different methods, perhaps it will be necessary to consider new ways and methods of instilling them into their psyche, forming them in the problem-based teaching method. The choice of literary material is also a sign of skill. For example, through A. Oripov's drama "Sahibqiron", the students are made to feel that Amir Temur's principles of loving the homeland, protecting it from any external influences, and defending it in practice through the interpretation of images.

Developing pedagogical ways of forming patriotism by making students imagine their future, introducing a mechanism to convince young people about their future. The student imagines his future without being proud of what his ancestors did in the past, as he enters the global education process, he prepares for the journey to the desired, conditional, probable future, his imagination expands. This is how self-confidence is formed in young people.

While trying to lead the student to a certain goal in literary education, it is necessary to travel to the inner world of the student, to penetrate deeper, to study the motives of individual interest. A stimulus is a social influence, while a motive is a personal need, desire of an activity caused by a stimulus.

As the main "executors" of the lesson are the student and the teacher, the student's motivation is the teacher who gives him a stimulus. Does today's teacher have enough skills to instill patriotic ideas in the minds of young people? What flaws in his professional maturity prevent the realization of these factors? What will happen if a student who hears one thing at school and witnesses other things in practice begins to distrust the reality of life?

If the formation of attitudes towards different ideas and views of students is carried out through the same method, the interest fades by itself. Especially about the issue of the sameness of the lesson in the process of literature education: "Constantly looking at the same thing leads to boredom and impatience. When education is organized in different ways, the student seems to be walking in a garden where different flowers have opened, before he sees one, another one begins, and the child is interested in them, wants to see them, as it is said: "Every new thing has a taste." The same actions tire people and lead to change of activity.

Knowledge given ready is quickly forgotten. It is no secret that this is one of the disadvantages of traditional education. As long as the teacher aims to convey to his student the problems that need to be polished, which are waiting for their solution, and which are considered important to be learned and mastered, then the goal cannot be achieved if he does not organize the lesson in such a way as not to cause the student's desire to harden, that is, if he does not become a teacher of children. Already, "lightness in the educational process is like giving liquid food to a baby who cannot chew. However, for the proper growth of a child, it is more important to teach him to eat than to feed him. In the educational system, it is more important to teach a child to think

independently, reflect, and learn by working rather than to inform a child of this or that knowledge."

A modern teacher is the manager and director of the educational process. He will have to prepare in advance the method of skillfully passing the lesson, use different targeted methods and methods at each stage, it is necessary to create a scenario of the lesson like a screenwriter.

Story, conversation, lecture, problem-based learning, creating a problem situation, business exercises, educational exercises, debate, small research, inductive, deductive discussions, independent work with the source, programmed learning, pair work, small group work, SWOT analysis, specific situations, working with metaplankarta, presentation, working individually, in pairs, creating card files, working with pictures, about a hundred ways and methods are used in today's educational system in a unique way. They are used as a form of developing lesson technologies and help the teacher in revealing the essence of the subject.

Whether the teacher teaches the lesson in a traditional way or a modern way, some students laugh at the fact that their performance does not change, they continue to drag the whole class behind. In our opinion, a student does not understand a new topic if:

- a) when there is no correlation in the data;
- b) when they cannot explain terms and new words;
- c) when the material is simply read without entering into its content.

The above three cases of underachieving are caused by the teacher not being able to achieve the harmony of students' thinking, perception and practice (hand movements). If the students can combine and harmonize this human condition (of course, with the help of the teacher), the educational goal will be 100% realized. It seems that the achievement of the purpose of the lesson depends not only on the student's mastery, but also on the teacher's actions. The teacher should ensure that the student performs the following during the lesson:

- *cognitive activity*(related to knowledge, thinking) includes goals from remembering and restoring the learned material to problem solving, that is, the teaching goals set in the daily practice of the teacher and determines what the student thinks and knows;

- *psychomotor activity*(in the field of movement) - this direction is related to the formation of one or another type of movement (motor), manipulative activity, neuromuscular coordination. In this, the question "What does the student do?" is answered. Objectives can be reflected in the form of: writing skills, creative statement or essay, speaking skills, thinking through oral speech, doing in practice, etc.;

- *affective action*(emotional - in the field of values, feelings) includes the goals of forming emotional-personal relations to the environment, world events, from simple perception, interest, preparation for the task to the assimilation of values and attitudes, to their active manifestation. In this, the answer to the question "What does the student feel?" is found. These three actions, which form the basis of the educational system, determine the stages of the student's knowledge. Its essence is reflected in the following diagram:

Special organization of literature teaching at the stages of continuous education, radical renewal of the attitude to literary education, improvement of professional training and professionalism of literature teachers on the basis of new pedagogical requirements, and ensuring a healthy attitude to the ongoing changes should be strengthened. In this regard, in the process of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, special attention should be paid to the compatibility of need, desire and necessity. We are confident that educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is accepted as the main problem of general education, secondary special education systems, as well as higher education, which is very important for the future of the country.

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